

Real Time Human, Speed Breaks And Potholes Detection Using Machine Learning And OpenCV

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Abstract—The Real Time Human, Speed Breaks And Potholes Detection system is an advanced technology that can be used for real-time detection of speed breaks, potholes, and humans on the road. The system processes real-time video feeds from cameras mounted on moving cars or along the side of the road using computer vision algorithms. The video feeds are analyzed in real-time to identify any road surface anomalies, such as potholes and speed breaks, which can be hazardous to vehicles and pedestrians. The system combines thresholding approaches to find potholes and speed breaks while using the Histogram of Oriented Gradients (HOG) descriptor and person detector to find people on the road. It provides real-time alerts to drivers about anomalies on the road, such as speed breaks and potholes, to improve road safety, it can also warn drivers when there are anomalies on the road. The Real Time Human, Speed Breaks And Potholes Detection system has the potential to revolutionize road safety by providing real-time information about road surface conditions. The system can be installed on mobile phones as well as on the roadside, allowing for comprehensive Real Time Human, Speed Breaks And Potholes Detection. This technology can be useful for municipalities, transportation agencies, and emergency services, as it can help in the early detection of human, speed breaks, and potholes due to prevention of accidents caused by road surface.

Keywords—Road surface monitoring, Real-time detection, Speed breaks, Potholes, Human detection, Computer vision, Histogram of Oriented Gradients (HOG) descriptor, Person detector, Thresholding techniques, Road safety, Real-time alerts, Pedestrian detection, Vehicle-mounted cameras, Roadside cameras, Comprehensive monitoring, Municipalities, Transportation agencies, Emergency services, Accident prevention.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Road safety is a critical issue that affects millions of people widely. One of the major factors of accidents is poor road surface conditions, such as speed breaks and potholes. These hazards can cause accidents that cause harm to both property and individuals, including severe injuries and even fatalities. In addition to these physical road hazards, the presence of pedestrians on the road can also be a significant safety concern.

Traditional methods of monitoring road conditions, such as visual assessments and manual appraisals, are time-consuming and often ineffective. To address these challenges, the improvement of technology-based frameworks for Real Time Human, Speed Breaks And Potholes Location has picked up noteworthy consideration in later a long time. The Real Time Human, Speed Breaks And Potholes Detection system is an advanced technology that can be used ad

real time detection of speed breaks, potholes, and humans on the road. The system utilizes computer vision techniques to process live video feeds from cameras mounted on vehicles or on the roadside. By analyzing these feeds, the system can identify road surface anomalies that pose a safety risk to drivers and pedestrians.

The Real Time Human, Speed Breaks And Potholes Detection system has the potential to revolutionize road safety by providing real-time information about road surface conditions. This real time human, speed break, and pothole detection can be useful for municipalities, transportation agencies, and emergency services, as it can help in the early detection and prevention of accidents caused by road surface hazards. This Real Time Human, Speed Breaks And Potholes Detection system, including the computer vision techniques used for human, speed break, and pothole detection, and how it can improve road safety.

II. HISTOGRAM OF ORIENTED GRADIENTS (HOG)

The Histogram of Oriented Gradients (HOG) descriptor is a feature descriptor that extracts information about the edges and textures in an image.[7] It works by dividing an image into small cells and computing a histogram of gradient orientations within each cell. The histograms are then normalized over a larger block of cells, allowing the descriptor to be robust to variations in lighting and contrast.

In the context of human detection, the HOG descriptor is used in combination with a person detector,[4] which is a machine learning algorithm trained to recognize the patterns of human body parts. The HOG descriptor is applied to a sliding window of the image, and the resulting feature vector is fed into the person detector to determine whether the window contains a human or not.

Fig 1 : Human detection using HOG descriptor

In the context of Real Time Human, Speed Breaks And Potholes Detection, the HOG descriptor and person detector can be used to detect humans on or near the road, which could

be a safety hazard. By combining this with thresholding strategies to distinguish speed breaks and potholes, the framework can give a more comprehensive view of the street conditions and potential risks.

III. THRESHOLDING TECHNIQUE

Thresholding methods are utilized to portion an image into distinctive locales based on the concentrated or color values of its pixels.[8] Within the case of recognizing speed breaks and potholes on the street, ready to utilize thresholding to fragment the picture into ranges that compare to the road surface and ranges that compare to potential speed breaks or potholes. Usually regularly done by changing over the picture to a distinctive color space (such as HSV) and selecting a run of values that compare to the colors of the street and potential hazards. we utilize the `cv2.inRange()` work to make a cover for both speed breaks and potholes based on their comparing HSV color ranges. The resulting masks are at that point combined utilizing the `cv2.bitwise_or()` work to get a last veil that highlights both sorts of hazards. Once the dangers have been recognized, able to utilize advance picture preparing strategies (such as form location or format coordinating) to accurately find and characterize them.

IV. LITERATURE REVIEW

In recent years, the development of technology-based systems for Real Time Human, Speed Breaks And Potholes Discovery has picked up noteworthy consideration due to the potential for upgrading street security. The Real Time Human, Speed Breaks And Potholes Detection system is an advanced technology that can identify real time human, speed break, and pothole on the road.

One of the key technologies used in the Real Time Human, Speed Breaks And Potholes Detection system is computer vision. The system utilizes computer vision techniques, such as the Histogram of Oriented Gradients (HOG) descriptor, to process live video feeds from cameras mounted on vehicles or on the roadside. The HOG descriptor is a feature descriptor that is commonly used for object detection in computer vision.

In a study by Chen et al. (2016), the authors proposed a real-time Real Time Human, Speed Breaks And Potholes Detection system that utilized a camera mounted on a vehicle to detect road surface anomalies, including potholes, cracks, and patches. The system used a combination of color thresholding and edge detection to identify these anomalies. The system achieved the detection rate of 90% for potholes and 95% for cracks.[1]

In another study by Kim et al. (2017), the authors proposed a real-time pothole detection system that use an smartphone camera mounted on a vehicle. The system used a combination of template matching and machine learning algorithms to detect potholes. The system achieved a high detection rate of 95% for potholes.[2]

In a study by Tariq et al. (2020), the authors proposed a real-time speed breaker detection system that utilized a camera mounted on a vehicle. The system used a combination of image processing techniques and machine learning algorithms to detect speed breakers. The system achieved a high detection rate of 97% for speed breakers.[3].

The paper "Real-time Human Detection using Histograms of Oriented Gradients" by the authors N. Dalal, B. Triggs, and C. Schmid presents a method for real-time human detection using Histograms of Oriented Gradients (HOG). The authors find a method for computing the HOG features of an image and training a Support Vector Machine (SVM) classifier to detect humans. The study provides a comprehensive overview of the HOG method for human detection and presents experimental results demonstrating its effectiveness.[4]

The paper "Real-time pothole detection and classification using convolutional neural network" by Abdulrahman K. Ibrahim, Khaled A. Hussein, et al. (2020 IEEE 2nd International Conference on Computer Applications and Information Security (ICCAIS)) proposes a system for real-time potholes detection and classification on roads using a convolutional neural network (CNN). The system is evaluated on a dataset of road images captured from a vehicle, and achieves high accuracy for both pothole detection and severity classification. The authors also compare their system to other pothole detection methods, and show that their CNN-based approach outperforms them in terms of accuracy and efficiency.[5]

"Real-Time Human Detection using Histograms of Oriented Gradients and Support Vector Machines" by R. T. Collins, S. A. R. Fowlkes, and Y. Liu is a seminal paper in the field of real-time human detection. The paper presents a method for detecting people in real-time video streams using HOG and SVMs. The authors begin by describing the HOG feature descriptor, which computes the distribution of local gradient directions in an image. The HOG descriptor is used to create a feature vector for each subregion of an image, and these feature vectors are then used to train an SVM classifier. The authors then describe how the HOG feature descriptor and SVM classifier can be used for real-time human detection. The system works by sliding a detection window over the image and computing the HOG feature vector for each subregion of the image. These include vectors are at that point encouraged into the SVM classifier to decide whether or not the subregion contains a individual. The paper presents comes about on a assortment of datasets and appears that the HOG-SVM strategy accomplishes state-of-the-art execution in terms of both discovery precision and speed. The creators moreover illustrate the real-time execution of the framework on a live video stream.[6]

V. METHODOLOGY

The Real Time Human, Speed Breaks And Potholes Detection technique involves the use of computer vision techniques to detect speed breaks, potholes, and humans in real-time. The approach used involves capturing a video stream from a camera mounted on a vehicle, converting the video frames to the HSV color space,[9] and then thresholding the images to identify areas that correspond to speed breaks and potholes.

Contours of the objects in the image are then found using the `findContours` function in OpenCV,[10] and rectangles are drawn around the detected objects using the `boundingRect` function. The HOG (Histogram of Oriented Gradients)[7]

descriptor is used to detect humans in the image, and the detected boxes are displayed in the colour picture.

The output video is then written to a file using the VideoWriter function in OpenCV. The methodology enables real-time monitoring of street surfaces, which can be used to improve road safety by alerting drivers to unsafe conditions. The system can also be used to collect data on road conditions over time, which can be used to inform maintenance decisions and improve road infrastructure. Overall, the Real Time Human, Speed Breaks And Potholes Detection methodology provides an effective and efficient way to detect road conditions and improve road safety.

The Real Time Human, Speed Breaks And Potholes Detection using real-time speed break, pothole, and human detection typically involves the following steps:

- A) Setting the thresholds for detecting speed breaks and potholes.
- B) Initializing the HOG descriptor/person detector for human detection.
- C) Opening a webcam video stream and creating an output video writer.
- D) Reading the frame from the video stream and converting it to the HSV color space.
- E) Thresholding the HSV image to detect speed breaks and potholes.
- F) Combining the masks to detect both speed breaks and potholes.
- G) Finding the contours of the objects in the mask and drawing rectangles around the detected objects.
- H) Detecting people in the image using the HOG descriptor/person detector and drawing rectangles around the detected people.
- I) Writing the output video and displaying the resulting frame.
- J) Exiting the program if the 'q' key is pressed.

This technique combines computer vision techniques for detecting road hazards (speed breaks and potholes) with human detection using the HOG descriptor/person detector. It can be used to monitor road conditions in real-time monitoring for drivers of potential hazards.

A) Setting the thresholds for detecting speed breaks and potholes.

The thresholds for detection of speed breaks and potholes are utilization of two variables, namely, "speed_break_threshold" and "pothole_threshold". These variables are instrumental in identifying the range of pixel values that are viable for the recognition of both speed breaks and potholes in the HSV image of the road surface. The speed break threshold has been established as 50 units, implying that any pixel within the HSV image exhibiting a value below 205 (255 less 50) in the V channel shall be identified as a speed break. Similarly, the pothole threshold is set to 20, which means that any pixel in the HSV image with a value less than 235 (200-20) in the V channel will be considered as a pothole. By adjusting these thresholds, the sensitivity of the detection algorithm can be tuned to detect speed breaks and potholes of different sizes and shapes.

B) Initializing the HOG descriptor/person detector for human detection.

The HOG descriptor is used for detecting humans in the video stream. The HOG (Histogram of Oriented Gradients) descriptor [6] is a popular feature extraction method used for object detection in computer vision. It works by analyzing the distribution of edge directions in an image and using that information to create a feature vector that represents the object of interest.

The HOG descriptor/person detector is initialized using the OpenCV [10] library in Python. Specifically, the 'cv2.HOGDescriptor()' function is called to create a new HOG descriptor object, and the 'setSVMDetector()' method is used to load the default people detector for human detection. Once initialized, the HOG descriptor can be applied to each frame of the video stream to detect humans, and the resulting bounding boxes can be drawn on the image for visualization.

C) Opening a webcam video stream and creating an output video writer.

To begin with, a webcam connected to computer and install OpenCV library to access the camera stream and perform video processing.

1. Import the required libraries

```
import cv2
import numpy as np
```

2. Create a VideoCapture object to access the webcam:
cap = cv2.VideoCapture(0)
3. Define the video codec and create a VideoWriter object to save the processed video

```
out = cv2.VideoWriter('output.avi',
cv2.VideoWriter_fourcc(*'MJPG'),
15., (640, 480))
```

In here, we are using the XVID codec, setting the frame rate to 20 frames per second, and the video resolution to 640x480 pixels.

4. Start the video stream loop, capture frames, and process them.

while True:

```
ret, frame = cap.read()
out.write(frame.astype('uint8'))
# Exit if the 'q' key is pressed
if cv2.waitKey(1) == ord('q'):
    break
```

This loop reads frames from the camera stream using the 'cap.read()' function, performs your video processing code, writes the processed frame to the output video using the 'out.write(frame)' function, and displays the original frame using the 'cv2.imshow()' function. Pressing the "q" key exits the loop.

5. Release the resources and close the windows:

```
cap.release()
out.release()
cv2.destroyAllWindows()
cv2.waitKey(1)
```

This code releases the camera stream using the 'cap.release()' function, releases the output video using the 'out.release()' function, and closes all windows using the 'cv2.destroyAllWindows()' function.

D) Reading the frame from the video stream and converting it to the HSV color space.

The current frame from the video stream captured by the webcam and converts it from the default BGR color space to HSV using the cv2.cvtColor() function. This is done to make it easier to threshold the image and detect speed breaks and potholes.

E) Thresholding the HSV image to detect speed breaks and potholes.[11]

After converting the frame to the HSV color space, the code sets the thresholds for detecting speed breaks and potholes and creates masks for each using the cv2.inRange() function. The construction of the speed_break_mask involves the assignment of a lower threshold at the values (0, 0, 255 - speed_break_threshold) and an upper threshold at the values (255, 50, 255). "The pothole_mask is established through the application of a lower threshold encompassing values of 20, 70, and 200 minus the pothole_threshold, which is then paired with an upper threshold of 30, 255, and 255." These masks are combined using the cv2.bitwise_or() function to create a single mask for detecting both speed breaks and potholes.

```
# Set the thresholds for detect
speed_break_threshold = 50
pothole_threshold = 20
# Convert the frame to HSV color space
hsv = cv2.cvtColor(frame, cv2.COLOR_BGR2HSV)
# Threshold the HSV image to detect speed breaks and pot
speed_break_mask = cv2.inRange(hsv, (0, 0, 255 -
speed_break_threshold), (255, 50, 255))
pothole_mask = cv2.inRange(hsv, (20, 70, 200 -
pothole_threshold), (30, 255, 255))
# Combine the masks to detect both speed breaks and pot
mask = cv2.bitwise_or(speed_break_mask, pothole_mask)
```

This creates a binary mask where white pixels represent areas that are likely to be either speed breaks or potholes.

F) Combining the masks to detect both speed breaks and potholes.

After thresholding the HSV image to detect speed breaks and potholes, the masks for both are combined using a bitwise OR operation. This results in a single mask that detects both speed breaks and potholes in the frame.

G) Finding the contours of the objects in the mask and drawing rectangles around the detected objects.

After obtaining the binary mask for both speed breaks and potholes, the next step is to find the contours of the objects in the mask using the cv2.findContours() function. The

cv2.RETR_EXTERNAL flag specifies that only external contours should be detected, while the cv2.CHAIN_APPROX_SIMPLE flag compresses the contour by removing redundant points.

Then, for each contour found, a rectangle is drawn around it using the cv2.rectangle() function. The resulting rectangles represent the detected speed breaks and potholes in the current frame.

The code for finding the contours and drawing rectangles:

```
# Find the contours of the objects in the mask
contours, _ = cv2.findContours(mask,
cv2.RETR_EXTERNAL, cv2.CHAIN_APPROX_SIMPLE)
# Draw rectangles around the detected objects
for contour in contours:
x, y, w, h = cv2.boundingRect(contour)
cv2.rectangle(frame, (x, y), (x+w, y+h),
(0, 255, 0), 2)
```

H) Detecting people in the image using the HOG descriptor/person detector and drawing rectangles around the detected people.

```
boxes, weights = hog.detectMultiScale(frame,
winStride=(8,8) )
boxes = np.array([[x, y, x + w, y + h] for
(x, y, w, h) in boxes])
for (xA, yA, xB, yB) in boxes:
# display the detected boxes in the colour
cv2.rectangle(frame, (xA, yA), (xB, yB),
(0, 255, 0), 2)
```

After drawing rectangles around the detected objects, the code uses the HOG descriptor/person detector to detect people in the image. The detected bounding boxes for the people are drawn as rectangles around them.

I) Writing the output video and displaying the resulting frame.

```
# Write the output video
out.write(frame.astype('uint8'))
# Display the resulting frame
cv2.imshow('Speed Break, Pothole, and Human Detection',
frame)
```

Finally, the output video is written and the resulting frame is displayed in a window.

J) Exiting the program if the 'q' key is pressed.

The program uses the cv2.waitKey() function to wait for a key event and checks if the key pressed is 'q' using the ord() function. If the 'q' key is pressed, the program breaks out of the loop and releases the resources.

```
# Exit if the 'q' key is pressed
if cv2.waitKey(1) == ord('q'):
break
```

VI. RESULT AND ANALYSIS

The Real Time Human, Speed Breaks And Potholes Detection that uses computer vision techniques to detect speed breaks, potholes, and humans in real-time using a webcam video stream. The script uses the HOG descriptor for human detection and HSV color space thresholding to detect speed breaks and potholes.

```
import cv2
import numpy as np
```

The script starts by setting the thresholds for detecting speed breaks and potholes. These thresholds are used to create masks for each of the road hazards. The script then initializes the HOG descriptor/person detector for detecting humans.

Fig 2: User interface screen

The script opens a webcam video stream and starts a loop to process each frame in real-time. For each frame, the script converts the frame to the HSV color space and applies the speed break and pothole masks to detect these hazards. The masks are combined to detect both hazards simultaneously. The script then finds the contours of the objects in the mask and draws rectangles around the detected objects. The script also detects humans in the image using the HOG descriptor and draws rectangles around the detected humans. Finally, the script writes the output video to a file and displays the resulting frame with the detected hazards and humans. Finally we can observe the output video to see how well the script detects speed breaks, potholes, and humans. we can also adjust the threshold values for detecting these hazards to optimize the detection accuracy. Overall, this script can be used as a starting point for building a more advanced road monitoring system that can detect and analyze road conditions in real-time to improve road safety.

Fig 3: Detect Human, speed break and pothole.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper, Real Time Human, Speed Breaks And Potholes Detection system for real-time detection of speed breaks, potholes, and humans is a useful tool for improving road safety. The methodology involves setting thresholds for detecting speed breaks and potholes, initializing the HOG descriptor/person detector for human detection, opening a webcam video stream, and creating an output video writer.

The system then reads the frame from the video stream, converts it to the HSV color space, thresholds the HSV image to detect speed breaks and potholes, combines the masks to detect both speed breaks and potholes, finds the contours of the objects in the mask, and draws rectangles around the detected objects. Finally, the system detects people in the image using the HOG descriptor/person detector, draws rectangles around the detected people, writes the output video, and displays the resulting frame. This system can help to reduce accidents and injuries caused by road conditions, making roads safer for all users.

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